

Mars 2020 SHERLOC/WATSON

Perseverance's SHERLOC WATSON – post-landing refinement of relations between focus, range, and image scale using images acquired on Mars, plus an update on particulates on the detector

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October 2021
Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5555292>

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1. Introduction

The SHERLOC (Scanning Habitable Environments with Raman and Luminescence for Organics and Chemicals) WATSON (Wide Angle Topographic Sensor for Operations and eNginEering) camera is located on the turret at the end of the *Perseverance* rover's robotic arm (**Figure 1**; Bhartia et al., 2021). *Perseverance* landed in western Jezero crater, Mars, on 18 February 2021. WATSON is a copy of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) onboard the *Curiosity* rover that has been operating in Gale crater, Mars, since August 2012.

Figure 1. WATSON camera head on the SHERLOC Turret Assembly on Mars. This is a portion of *Perseverance* left navigation camera image NLF_0017_0668452386_425FDR_N0030578NCAM00183_0M00LLJ03, acquired on 08 March 2021 in Jezero crater. The inset shows *Perseverance* as seen by a camera onboard the *Ingenuity* helicopter on Sol 64 (25 April 2021; image HSF_0064_0672622216_406ECM_N0030001HELI00002_000085J02).

The most important attribute a WATSON data user wants to know is the scale of features captured in a WATSON image. The scale is directly related to the camera working distance (range between the subject and the front lens element) and lens focus position. Lens focus is reported by the instrument as a stepper motor count. Thus, the motor count for a given image is related to working distance and scale. This holds true for images acquired over the typical camera operation ranges (working distances) between ~2.5 and ~40 cm (typical based on MSL MAHLI; Yingst et al., 2016). As working distance goes from ~40 cm to ~210 cm, smaller motor

count steps per centimeter of range increase the uncertainty in knowledge of working distance as derived from motor count. As the distance increases past ~210 cm, focus approaches and then reaches infinity and motor count is not a reliable indicator of distance and scale. The same is true for working distances less than ~2.5 cm; motor count becomes a less reliable indicator of range and scale as the lens approaches its minimum focus range around 1.8 cm (subjects closer than 1.8 cm cannot be imaged in focus).

Each WATSON or MAHLI camera is slightly different in terms of mechanical relations between motor count and lens focus, as well as performance at the minimum working distance and at infinity focus (the WATSON on Mars performs better than the MAHLI on Mars at both of these extreme ends of the focus range; Edgett et al., 2019). Thus, the relation between motor count and working distance must be determined empirically for each such camera. Experience gained from working with the MSL MAHLI since it was assembled in 2008 (Edgett et al., 2012; Edgett et al., 2015) showed that pixel scale is also best determined empirically by acquiring images focused on targets of known scale at known distances that span the operative range (~2.5 to ~210 cm).

The relations between motor count, working distance, and pixel scale were determined for *Perseverance*'s WATSON using data acquired in a clean room environment in October 2019 (Edgett et al., 2019). However, given typical pre-launch schedule and resource constraints, data collection over working distances in the 40 to 210 cm range was minimal (and this was acceptable, at the time, because most imaging will occur on Mars in the 2.5 to 40 cm range). MAHLI experience showed that acquiring additional images on Mars to help characterize the relation between motor count and working distance—both over the 40–210 cm range as well as spot-checks in the 2.5–40 cm range—can lead to a substantive improvement in knowledge of the relation between motor count, working distance, and pixel scale. For MSL MAHLI, the values reported by Edgett et al. (2012) were retired in 2015, and the refined values determined by Edgett et al. (2015) have been in use ever since.

This report provides refined knowledge, expressed as equations and their relevant coefficients, for the relations between motor count, working distance, and pixel scale for the WATSON camera onboard the *Perseverance* rover, currently operating in Jezero crater. This analysis uses both the original data acquired on Earth in October 2019 and new data acquired on Mars during March through July 2021.

This report also provides a post-landing update regarding knowledge of the foreign object debris (FOD) that occurs on the WATSON CCD (charge-coupled device) detector.

2. Key documents

Key preceding documents are the WATSON characterization and calibration report (Edgett et al., 2019) and the SHERLOC investigation description paper (Bhartia et al., 2021). Both of these provide a pre-launch assessment of the knowledge of FOD on the CCD and the relation between focus motor count, target range (working distance), and image pixel scale.

- Edgett, K.S., et al. (2019) Mars 2020 Perseverance SHERLOC WATSON camera pre-delivery characterization and calibration report. Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18447.00165>
- Bhartia, R., et al. (2021) Perseverance's Scanning Habitable Environments with Raman and Luminescence for Organics and Chemicals (SHERLOC) investigation. *Space Science Reviews*, 217, 58. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-021-008102-z>

Because WATSON is a copy of the MSL MAHLI, papers that describe MAHLI hardware (DiBiase and Laramee, 2009; Ghaemi, 2009; Edgett et al., 2012; Edgett et al., 2015) and how MAHLI has been operated on Mars (Minitti et al., 2013; Edgett et al., 2015; Yingst et al., 2016), are also applicable.

3. Brief instrument description

3.1 Overview

WATSON is one of the two visible wavelength imaging (camera) subsystems of the SHERLOC instrument suite (Bhartia et al., 2021) onboard the Mars 2020 rover, *Perseverance* (Farley et al., 2020). Located on the SHERLOC Turret Assembly (STA) mounted on the turret at the end of *Perseverance's* robotic arm (**Figure 1**), WATSON is a color camera with a focusable macro lens. It can focus on targets at working distances of ~ 1.78 cm to infinity with pixel scales ranging from as high as ~ 13.1 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ at ~ 1.8 cm range to ~ 100 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ at ~ 25.9 cm range to even lower resolution at infinity focus (Edgett et al., 2019). An image of the WATSON camera head acquired on Mars is shown in **Figure 2**.

WATSON is being used on Mars to obtain science data in the form of close-up (macrophotographic) images of geological materials at scales ranging from ~ 14 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ to > 100 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ and to acquire science-enabling engineering images to support core sample extraction and rover and science instrument hardware inspections and diagnostics. WATSON images of geological targets include provision of context for Mars Sample Return core samples and SHERLOC and PIXL (Planetary Instrument for X-ray Lithochemistry) spectroscopy.

As noted, WATSON is a build-to-print copy of the MSL MAHLI. Any exceptions to the build-to-print nature of the instrument resulted from electronic parts availability a decade after fabrication of the MSL MAHLI. Unlike the *Curiosity* rover and its MAHLI, *Perseverance* carries no dedicated calibration target for WATSON. The instrument team, instead, makes use of the SHERLOC (Bhartia et al., 2021), PIXL (Allwood et al., 2020), and Mastcam-Z (Kinch et al., 2020) calibration targets.

Figure 2. WATSON camera head on Mars, dust cover closed, with all LEDs illuminated. Look closely to see violet illumination emitted by the UV LEDs. Mastcam-Z image ZLF_0017_0668453139_217FDR_N0030578-ZCAM05002_1100LUJ01, acquired on 08 March 2021.

3.2 Stepper motor and lens focus

WATSON can focus on targets at working distances $\geq \sim 1.8$ cm with the dust cover open or closed (Edgett et al., 2019; Bhartia et al., 2021). It can be autofocused or focused manually. It can also acquire focus stack images. Manual focus is performed by commanding the lens focus group to move to a specific motor count position.

Autofocus is determined by acquiring a commanded number of images (usually 10–30) at different focus positions that bound (with margin) the focus position of the planned/anticipated working distance. This acquisition is followed by quality 80/100 grayscale JPEG compression (Joint Photographic Experts Group; see CCITT (1993)) and rapid, onboard analysis of the resulting compressed file sizes. The apex of the parabola fit to JPEG file size versus stepper motor count for the single least compressed image, the preceding image, and the succeeding image, determines the focus position (see Figure 23 of Edgett et al., 2012). The motor then moves the lens focus group to that position and a focused image is acquired. The images obtained to determine focus via JPEG compression are not retained.

In practice, because targets can have varied relief across the field of view, autofocus is often best performed using a sub-frame of the full 1600 x 1200-pixel scene. On Mars, this is usually (although not exclusively) a sub-frame of 480 x 480 pixels located at the center of the CCD. This approach, used routinely for MSL MAHLI and for WATSON in Jezero crater, ensures that all or a portion of the center of a full-frame scene is in focus. Following autofocus sub-frame acquisition, the larger (*i.e.*, full frame) image is acquired. Focus stack acquisition can, likewise, be commanded to be based upon the preceding autofocused position.

3.2.1 Stepper motor actions

WATSON dust cover motion and focus are actuated by a single Cobham (formerly Aeroflex) 10 mm stepper motor per the design of DiBiase and Laramée (2009). Image focus is, thus, directly related to stepper motor count. In turn, the range or working distance is related to motor count for in-focus elements in a resulting image. **Figure 3** illustrates the actions that occur over the range between 0 and 16000 motor count steps (again, see DiBiase and Laramée, 2009, for technical details). At motor count 0, a Hall Effect sensor detects that the mechanism is in its launch restraint position and that WATSON is in a mechanically safe state for rover motion (*e.g.*, driving), Mars sample extraction (coring), as well as (before arrival on Mars) launch and landing.

Figure 3. WATSON mechanism behavior as a function of stepper motor count. The mechanism launch restraint is at motor count 0. The (H) symbols indicate the location of Hall Effect sensors that confirm mechanical configuration relative to reported motor count.

When in the launch restraint position, the lens is in focus at its minimum working distance and imaging can be performed through the transparent dust cover (although the window on the dust cover became coated with a thin film of dust during the rover’s final descent to Mars on 18 February 2021; see **Figures 2 and 4**).

When the stepper motor is activated, the motor counts increase or decrease on command, one increment (one step) at a time. With the dust cover remaining closed, the lens focus group first moves from its minimum working distance focus position to its maximum (in focus at infinity). Then the cover begins to open. When fully open, the camera is again in focus at its minimum working distance. To focus on targets with the cover fully open, the motor steps backward toward the 12000 motor counts position. A Hall Effect sensor located in the middle of the dust cover open focus range confirms the physical position of the lens focus group relative to stepper motor count.

The correspondence between motor count and focus position (which translates to working distance and pixel scale) is unique to a given WATSON or MAHLI camera head and requires empirical determination.

3.2.2 Stepper motor count reportage

For each image acquired, WATSON reports the focus motor count position at which it was acquired. For example, a reported motor count (m) of 13992 is 13,992 steps from the $m = 0$ launch restraint position. From **Figure 3**, one can see that an image obtained at motor count 13996 is one in which the dust cover was open during acquisition.

Manual commanding of a focus position requires that the motor count be expressed as a multiple of 6. The WATSON autofocus algorithm (see Edgett et al., 2012; Edgett et al., 2015) also operates on a multiple-of-6 basis. In this regard, WATSON autofocus differs from that of MSL MAHLI; WATSON autofocusing rounds the computed focus motor count position to the nearest multiple of 6.

Figure 4. During terminal descent to the Martian surface on 18 February 2021, as expected, the transparent window of the WATSON dust cover became coated with a thin film of dust. MSL MAHLI experience suggests that this coating will remain on the dust cover for the duration of the surface mission (on MSL, it has remained in place for more than 3160 sols). **(a)** WATSON image S10_0018_0668555666_001ECM_N0030578SRLC-08001_0000LUJ03, acquired with the dust cover closed on 09 March 2021; **(b)** image of the same target, S10_0018_0668555815_008ECM_-N0030578SRLC08001_0000LUJ03, acquired with the dust cover open, also on 09 March 2021.

WATSON operations personnel monitor the performance of the stepper motor relative to the actual position of the movable lens focus group using the mid-range and launch restraint Hall Effect sensors. Motor count “skipping” or “sticking” can occur on some occasions at very cold temperatures; this refers to a case in which the focus group detected a Hall sensor at a motor count different from expectation. This problem is avoided at nominal operating temperatures; however, when this occurs, it is possible that the motor count position reported by the instrument does not actually indicate the lens focus position.

4. Refinement – relation of motor count to range (working distance)

Knowledge of the scale of features observed in a WATSON close-up image is vital to scientific interpretation. A common practice on Earth is to place an object of known scale in the field of view and photograph it along with the geological target. For WATSON on Mars, this is not possible but some Mars 2020 rover hardware (e.g., coring device, abrasion tool, rover wheels) can create markings of known scale that will be captured in some WATSON images.

Determination of WATSON image scale (**Section 5**) first requires knowledge of the camera working distance and focus range. Working distance is independently valuable in cases in which rover operators may desire to use the camera as a range-finder for subsequent instrument or tool placement via the robotic arm, as has occasionally been performed using the MSL MAHLI (Minitti et al., 2013; Yingst et al., 2016). Range is a term often used in the context of focus stack images. Because WATSON focus stack images are acquired without moving the camera (i.e., the distance between the lens and the subject—the working distance—does not change), range is inclusive of working distance but also describes the distances implied by the presence of in-focus elements in each given focus stack image.

The purpose of this investigation is to refine knowledge of the relation between the camera’s stepper motor count and working distance or range. The relation between motor count (m) and working distance (d_w) is determined for cases in which an image is acquired when the WATSON dust cover is open or closed. This section also reviews the knowledge of the minimum working distance at which the camera can focus, as well as the opposite—the stepper motor counts at which the camera is focused at infinity.

4.1 Minimum working distance

The minimum working distance at which the WATSON onboard Perseverance can focus is 1.78 ± 0.1 cm. This result was obtained before launch and is unchanged in this report.

Knowledge of the minimum working distance at which the *Perseverance* WATSON can acquire in-focus images was measured using pre-launch data by Edgett et al. (2019) and found to be

$d_w = 1.78 \pm 0.01$ cm. At this distance, the images have a pixel scale (p) of 13.1 ± 0.1 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$. It is very important to note that, on Mars, WATSON will never be purposefully positioned as close as 1.78 cm working distance because doing so, with *Perseverance*'s robotic arm, puts the instrument at risk of colliding with the target. Routine MSL MAHLI operations usually place the camera no closer than about 2.9 cm at a natural, geological target.

The analysis of minimum working distance determined before launch does not require refinement on Mars (and, as noted, would be nearly impossible to perform on Mars), thus no new analysis is reported here and the pre-launch determination stands.

4.2 Infinity focus motor count positions

Pre-launch assessment and recommendations for WATSON infinity focus motor count positions were:

- *dust cover closed (m_{closed}) = 4890*
- *dust cover open (m_{open}) = 12000*

WATSON images of the Martian landscape acquired on Sols 11 and 130 demonstrated that these recommendations are stable and provide excellent infinity-focused views.

4.2.1 Pre-launch knowledge

Using the pre-launch data described by Edgett et al. (2019), the following motor count positions were recommended for manual commanding of WATSON infinity focus:

- Dust cover open infinity manual focus position = $m_{\text{open}} = 12000$
- Dust cover closed infinity manual focus position = $m_{\text{closed}} = 4890$.

These positions are within the margins necessary such that the dust cover will not begin to open when focusing it at infinity with the dust cover closed, nor begin to close when focusing it at infinity with the dust cover open.

Pre-launch analysis also found that, unlike MSL MAHLI, WATSON images are in focus at infinity over a large range of motor count positions between the dust-cover-open and dust-cover-closed states. As Edgett et al. (2019) said, the camera is in focus at infinity between motor counts of 12018 to 10524 when the dust cover is open, and 4818 to 8034 when the dust cover is closed. In addition, between positions 8034 and 10524, the camera is barely (to human visual perception) out of focus.

4.2.2 Post-landing assessment

The fact that WATSON can focus at infinity over a large range of motor count positions, particularly over a range where MSL MAHLI images go out of focus “beyond” infinity (Edgett et al., 2015), also means that an infinity autofocus test similar to that performed for MAHLI (Edgett et al., 2015) cannot be performed, because autofocus will fail to find an infinity focus position because images do not blur “beyond” infinity.

Thus, to confirm the pre-launch understanding of WATSON infinity focus behavior (testing for which was performed in a laboratory by imaging a target at 836 cm range, rather than viewing a landscape receding toward a horizon), WATSON acquired a suite of images of the Martian landscape that were manually focused around the recommended m_{open} value of 12000 for the dust cover open case, and a m_{closed} value of 4890 for the dust cover closed case.

The dust-cover open infinity focus test was performed on Sol 130. With the robotic arm stowed, WATSON obtained a 6-image manual focus stack at motor count intervals of 72 centered on the recommended m_{open} value of 12000 (**Table 1**). Because the dust cover became coated with a thin film of dust during the rover’s terminal descent (**Figure 4**), it is likely that dust-cover-closed images of the landscape will rarely (if ever again) be acquired. As a result of that assessment, the infinity focus test for the dust cover closed case consisted only of acquisition of manually focused views of the Martian landscape at m_{closed} 4890. The cover-closed case was performed twice (**Table 1**), once on Sol 11 (**Figure 5**) and again on Sol 130 (**Figure 6**). The latter can be compared with the dust cover open infinity focus images of the same scene.

Table 1. WATSON post-landing infinity focus test images			
sol	image ID	manual focus motor count	results
<i>dust cover closed</i>			
11	SI0_0011_0667926298_145ECM_N0030000SRLC08000_0000LMJ01	4890	good focus, considering dust cover was coated with a film of dust.
130	SI0_0130_0678477449_531ECM_N0042222SRLC08005_0000LUJ01	4890	good focus, considering dust cover was still coated with a film of dust.
<i>dust cover open</i>			
130	SI1_0130_0678477264_269ECM_N0042222SRLC08005_0000LUJ01	12216	image not in focus.
130	SI1_0130_0678477278_054ECM_N0042222SRLC08005_0000LUJ02	12144	image not in focus on distant landforms
130	SI1_0130_0678477292_507ECM_N0042222SRLC08005_0000LUJ01	12072	good focus over entire image
130	SI1_0130_0678477306_070ECM_N0042222SRLC08005_0000LUJ01	12000	good focus over entire image
130	SI1_0130_0678477320_027ECM_N0042222SRLC08005_0000LUJ01	11928	good focus over entire image
130	SI1_0130_0678477334_113ECM_N0042222SRLC08005_0000LUJ01	11856	good focus over entire image

Infinity focus performance when the dust cover is closed, at m_{closed} 4890, is as expected (**Figures 5 and 6**) and compares well (except for the film of dust on the dust cover) with the dust cover open infinity performance (**Figure 6**).

Infinity focus performance when the dust cover is open is also as expected (**Table 1, Figures 6 and 7**). The images acquired on Sol 130 at motor counts 12216 and 12144 are not in focus at infinity. The others, at motor counts 12072, 12000, 11928, and 11856, are in focus at infinity, consistent with pre-launch analysis (although a pre-launch image at 12072 was not acquired, that it is in focus at infinity is not surprising).

The Sol 130 infinity focus test image series also provided an interesting science observation; a dust-raising event occurred in the distance, in front of the distal landforms (Jezero delta and northwest crater wall). Dust is first raised between the images acquired at motor counts 12072 and 12000, then raised dust patterns change in the subsequent two images, the last of which shows two plumes or perhaps dust devils (**Figure 7**).

Figure 5. Left: WATSON Sol 11 (02 March 2021) infinity focus test image of the landscape in Jezero crater acquired at a manual focus position of m_{closed} 4890 with the dust cover closed. **Right:** Same image, following rudimentary image processing to show color and contrast. Note that a flat field was not applied. This is WATSON image SIO_0011_0667926298_145ECM_N0030000SRLC08000_0000LMJ01.

Figure 6. Left: WATSON Sol 130 (02 July 2021) infinity focus test image of a landscape in Jezero crater acquired at a manual focus position of m_{closed} 4890 with the dust cover closed (image S10_0130_0678477449_531ECM_N-0042222SRLC08005_0000LUJ01). **Right:** Same scene as viewed with infinity focus at m_{open} 12000 with the dust cover open (image S11_0130_0678477306_070ECM_N0042222SRLC08005_0000LUJ01). The distance across the rover wheel tracks in the near field is ~ 2.7 m from one side to the other.

Figure 7. Sub-frames of the dust-cover-open Sol 130 WATSON infinity focus test images with manually-focused motor counts in blue at upper left (image identifiers in yellow at bottom). The first two images, at motor counts 12216 and 12144, are not in focus at infinity, as expected based on pre-launch analysis. The images at 12072 through 11856 are in focus at infinity, as expected from pre-launch analysis (a pre-launch image at 12072 was not obtained, thus this result is not surprising but not captured in pre-launch observations).

4.3 Range (working distance) from motor count – dust cover open

The analysis described here integrates data acquired on both Mars and Earth and presents revised coefficients that describe the relation between working distance (d_w , in centimeters) and stepper motor count (m_{open}) when the WATSON dust cover is open and elements of the WATSON image are in focus. Those new coefficients are:

$a = 1.09106 \times 10^6$, $b = -332.921$, $c = 3.82592 \times 10^{-2}$, $d = -1.96922 \times 10^{-6}$, and $e = 3.84562 \times 10^{-11}$,

in the following equation: $d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}$.

Nominal WATSON operations on Mars are performed with the dust cover open. Knowledge of the empirical relation between working distance and motor count is vital for determination of image scale (**Section 5**) and to command the camera for time- and resource-efficient operation on Mars. The relation between motor count and working distance differs for each WATSON or MAHLI camera unit. Thus, for example, one cannot apply the relations between motor count and working distance determined by Edgett et al. (2015) for MAHLI to *Perseverance*'s WATSON.

4.3.1 Pre-launch determination

Edgett et al. (2019) determined the relation between motor count and working distance for both the dust cover open and dust cover closed cases. This determination used data acquired in an ambient clean room setting at MSSS (Malin Space Science Systems) in October 2019. Most of the data were acquired at working distances between 1.75 and 850 cm. This effort involved imaging planar targets (e.g., **Figure 8**), oriented plane-parallel to the WATSON CCD, at known working distances (determined via laser range-finder). In each case, WATSON was commanded to autofocus on the target at each distance. For targets in which the field of view included objects besides the target, an autofocused sub-frame focused on the target was obtained. **Table 2** lists the pre-launch dust cover open data. The images are available from Edgett et al. (2021; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5090820>).

Figure 8. WATSON images of targets used to determine relations between motor count, working distance, and pixel scale on Earth before launch. **(a)** ISO-12233 Digital Resolution Still Camera Test Chart (Applied Image, Inc., product QA-702-1-P). **(b)** USAF-1951 resolution target (Applied Image, Inc., product T-202-P-OP). **(c)** Grid (1 mm pitch) target (Applied Image, Inc., product AP-G50-P-OP). **(d)** Variant of USAF-1951 target with color and slanted edge targets. **(e)** Variant of USAF-1951 target. **(f)** Slanted-edge targets mounted on wall at about 836 cm distance.

The following equation describes the empirical relation between m_{open} and d_w (in centimeters) that was determined from the pre-launch data (Edgett et al., 2019):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 699788$, $b = -217.911$, $c = 2.56035 \times 10^{-2}$, $d = -1.35136 \times 10^{-6}$, and $e = 2.71652 \times 10^{-11}$. **Equation 1** applies only to the WATSON camera onboard *Perseverance*, only when the dust cover is open, and only when the m_{open} is between ~ 12228 and 15420 . However, this equation, which was also reported by Bhartia et al. (2021), is now retired in favor of **Equation 2** (**Section 4.3.2**), the refined result reported here.

4.3.2 Post-landing refinement

Based on MSL MAHLI experience (Edgett et al., 2015), knowledge of the relation between motor count and working distance can be confirmed or refined by acquiring a nested suite of images on Mars using the robotic arm to position the camera over a relatively flat surface.

This exercise was performed on mission Sol 78 (10 May 2021) to refine knowledge of the relations between motor count, working distance, and pixel scale following the Sol 0 landing of *Perseverance* in Jezero crater. A suite of dust-cover-open images, with each higher spatial resolution image nested within lower resolution views (**Figure 9**), was acquired to image a rock target named *Nataani* (the name was derived for Mars rover commanding from the Navajo word, *naat'áanii*, meaning leader or leadership). The robotic arm Facility Contact Sensor (FCS; see Moeller et al., 2021) first contacted the rock to establish the location of its surface in three-dimensional space. Then the robotic arm positioned WATSON at working distances of 25 cm, 6 cm (with an offset for a stereopair), and 3.7 cm, followed by an explicit nested suite at working distances of 210, 200, 170, 150, 100, 70, 40, 27, 17, 10, and 7 cm.

At each camera position, WATSON first acquired a 480 x 480-pixel autofocus sub-frame, followed by a full-frame image. Because the data were acquired under typical Mars environment conditions, illuminated by sunlight, and facilitated by an FCS touch, experience from MSL suggests that the larger working distance images (> 40 cm) are likely as reliable as the data acquired before launch in the cleanroom setting at MSSS.

The Sol 78 WATSON images of *Nataani* (**Figure 9**) are listed in **Table 3**. The listed working distance uncertainties are based on the assessment in **Section 4.5.2**; the pixel scale measurements in **Table 3** are described in **Section 5**.

The data acquired on Mars lead to an improvement in the understanding of the relation between m_{open} and d_w :

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (2)$$

in which $a = 1.09106 \times 10^6$, $b = -332.921$, $c = 3.82592 \times 10^{-2}$, $d = -1.96922 \times 10^{-6}$, and $e = 3.84562 \times 10^{-11}$.

Table 2. Pre-launch *Perseverance* WATSON dust cover OPEN motor count, working distance, and pixel scale observations

date acquired	image ID	motor count	laser range-finding measurement of working distance (cm)	pixel scale measured from image ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa059	15438	1.84	13.3 \pm 0.1
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa058	15192	2.09	14.2 \pm 0.1
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa057	15012	2.35	15.2 \pm 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa056	14880	2.60	16.2 \pm 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa055	14736	2.86	17.1 \pm 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa054	14622	3.11	18.1 \pm 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa053	14520	3.36	19.1 \pm 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa052	14334	3.87	21.0 \pm 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa051	14160	4.38	22.9 \pm 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa050	14046	4.89	24.7 \pm 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa049	13932	5.40	26.7 \pm 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa048	13830	5.90	28.4 \pm 0.1
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa046	13608	7.17	33.2 \pm 0.1
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa045	13470	8.44	37.6 \pm 0.2
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa044	13338	9.71	42.2 \pm 0.2
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa043	13224	10.98	46.8 \pm 0.3
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa038	13080	13.52	55.8 \pm 0.6
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa037	12966	16.06	64.6 \pm 0.8
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa036	12876	18.60	73.9 \pm 1.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa073	12750	23.68	91.6 \pm 2.6
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa074	12606	31.30	119 \pm 4
9-Oct-2019	wsfocusc013	12576	33.72	n/a
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa076	12546	38.92	147 \pm 7
09-Oct-2019	wsfocusc017	12516	41.72	n/a
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa079	12480	46.54	171 \pm 9
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusb004	12462	54.16	197 \pm 17
09-Oct-2019	wsfocusc021	12450	52.92	n/a
07-Oct-2019	wsfarfocusa003	12294	130.12	n/a
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusb005	12258	177.82	n/a
07-Oct-2019	wsfarfocusa005	12216	230.42	n/a
07-Oct-2019	wsfarfocusa007	12168	329.32	n/a
07-Oct-2019	wsfarfocusa009	12126	427.92	n/a
07-Oct-2019	wsfarfocusa012	12018	836.22	n/a

Figure 9. The Sol 78 (10 May 2021) nested suite of WATSON images of the rock target, Nataani, used to refine understanding of the relations between stepper motor count, working distance, and pixel scale. Successively inward from the outer edge of the figure are images at working distances of 210, 200, 170, 150, 100, 70, 40, 27, 25, 17, 10, 7, 6 (stereo pair; 2 images), and 3.7 cm. The corresponding image IDs are listed in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Sol 78 WATSON dust cover <u>OPEN</u> focus range test at rock target name Nataani – motor count, working distance, and pixel scale observations				
date acquired	image ID	motor count	working distance (cm)	pixel scale measured from image (µm/pixel)
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673881007_535ECM_N0032430SRLC00490_0000LUJ01	14400 ± 15	3.7 ± 0.1	n/a
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673880658_343ECM_N0032430SRLC00660_0000LUJ01	13794 ± 15	6.0 ± 0.1	n/a
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673880828_328ECM_N0032430SRLC00660_0000LUJ01	13794 ± 15	6.0 ± 0.1	n/a
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673883111_398ECM_N0032430SRLC00700_0000LUJ01	13626 ± 15	7.0 ± 0.1	n/a
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673882985_457ECM_N0032430SRLC01000_0000LUJ01	13296 ± 15	10.0 ± 0.1	n/a
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673882865_410ECM_N0032430SRLC01700_0000LUJ01	12906 ± 15	17.0 ± 0.2	n/a
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673880527_574ECM_N0032430SRLC02500_0000LUJ01	12696 ± 15	25.0 ± 0.3	n/a
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673882752_390ECM_N0032430SRLC02700_0000LUJ01	12666 ± 15	27.0 ± 0.3	n/a
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673882649_425ECM_N0032430SRLC04000_0000LUJ01	12516 ± 15	40.0 ± 0.4	149 ± 2
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673882176_390ECM_N0032430SRLC08002_0000LUJ01	12378 ± 15	70 ± 1	253 ± 5
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673882065_550ECM_N0032430SRLC08002_0000LUJ01	12312 ± 15	100 ± 1	355 ± 5
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673881952_390ECM_N0032430SRLC08002_0000LUJ01	12246 ± 15	150 ± 1	528 ± 10
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673881849_437ECM_N0032430SRLC08002_0000LUJ01	12228 ± 15	170 ± 1	607 ± 14
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673881736_437ECM_N0032430SRLC08002_0000LUJ01	12198 ± 15	200 ± 1	714 ± 20
10-May-2021	SI1_0078_0673881630_437ECM_N0032430SRLC08002_0000LUJ01	12192 ± 15	210 ± 1	733 ± 18

Equation 2 is the equation that should now be used, instead of **Equation 1**. **Equation 2** applies only to the WATSON camera head onboard *Perseverance*, only when the dust cover is open, and only when m_{open} is between ~ 12204 and ~ 14934 . The equation is best used for cases in which d_w is in the 2.5 to ~ 210 cm range and performs best for targets in the 2.5–40 cm range.

Figures 10 and 11 summarize the results—presented in this section plus **Sections 4.4 and 4.5**—regarding the refined relation between motor count and working distance. Relative to **Equation 1**, **Equation 2** provides an improved conversion of m_{open} to d_w for targets at ranges 150–170 cm and performs better for targets out to 210 cm. However, most WATSON imaging will be performed at close range, at working distances between 2.5 and 40 cm. Over that range, both equations perform the same (**Table 4**). The change to **Equation 2** is mainly aimed at improving understanding of the relation between motor count and working distance at larger ranges (see improvement by comparing values in **Table 4**). Owing to the large depth of field at greater working distances, when the target is at a distance greater than about 40 cm, a small change in motor count can result in a large change in knowledge of the range. Uncertainties are discussed in more detail in **Section 4.5**.

Figure 10. Refined relation between working distance, motor count (dust cover open and closed; solid curve; **Equations 2 and 3**), and depth of field (dotted black curves; **Equation 5**) for the WATSON onboard *Perseverance*. Blue dots are data acquired in October 2019 on Earth (**Table 2**); red dots are from data acquired on Sol 78 at *Nataani* on Mars (**Table 3**). Where “error bars” are unseen, they are smaller than the plotted data point dot.

Figure 11. Refined relation between working distance, motor count (dust cover open and closed; solid curve; **Equations 2 and 3**), and depth of field (dotted black curves; **Equation 5**) for small working distances (to 10 cm) for the WATSON onboard *Perseverance*. Blue dots are data acquired in October 2019 on Earth (**Table 2**); red dots are from data acquired on Sol 78 at *Nataani* on Mars (**Table 3**). Where “error bars” are unseen, they are smaller than the plotted data point dot.

Table 4. Comparison of estimated range and scale from motor count (dust cover open) using pre-launch and post-landing equations and coefficients over the operative working distances of 2.5 to 210 cm

actual working distance (cm)	motor count (divisible by 6)	pre-launch equations (Edgett et al., 2019; Bhartia et al. 2021)				post-landing equations (this report)			
		range (working dist.)		pixel scale		range (working dist.)		pixel scale	
		cm	± cm	µm/pixel	± µm/pixel	cm	± cm	µm/pixel	± µm/pixel
2.5	14928	2.5	0.1	15.9	0.2	2.5	0.1	15.8	0.1
3.0	14670	3.0	0.1	17.7	0.2	3.0	0.1	17.7	0.2
4.0	14286	4.0	0.1	21.4	0.3	4.0	0.1	21.4	0.4
5.0	14016	5.0	0.1	25.0	0.4	5.0	0.1	25.0	0.7
6.0	13806	6.0	0.2	28.7	0.6	6.0	0.1	28.7	0.9
7.0	13644	7.0	0.2	32.3	0.7	7.0	0.1	32.3	1.2
8.0	13512	8.0	0.3	36.0	0.9	8.0	0.1	35.9	1.4
9.0	13404	9.0	0.3	39.6	1.1	9.0	0.1	39.5	1.7
10.0	13308	10.0	0.4	43.4	1.4	10.0	0.2	43.2	2.0
15.0	13002	15.0	0.8	61.6	2.8	15.0	0.3	61.3	3.3
20.0	12828	20.0	1.4	79.9	4.9	20.1	0.6	79.3	4.7
25.0	12714	25.0	2.1	98.4	7.7	25.1	0.8	97.2	6.1
30.0	12636	29.9	3.0	116.2	10.8	30.0	1.1	114.2	7.4
35.0	12576	34.9	4.0	134.5	14.7	35.0	1.4	131.4	8.8
40.0	12528	40.1	5.3	153.5	19.4	40.0	1.8	148.9	10.2
50.0	12456	51.0	8.6	193.5	31.3	50.4	2.7	184.6	13.2
60.0	12408	61.8	12.6	232.8	45.9	60.4	3.6	218.5	16.1
70.0	12372	73.0	17.6	273.7	64.3	70.3	4.8	252.4	18.9
80.0	12342	85.5	24.3	319.7	88.9	81.1	6.1	289.1	22.0
90.0	12324	95.2	30.3	355.0	110.8	89.0	7.2	316.3	24.3
100.0	12306	107.1	38.8	398.5	141.8	98.4	8.7	348.9	27.0
120.0	12276	134.6	63.6	499.0	232.7	118.8	12.2	420.2	32.8
140.0	12252	168.3	107.2	622.4	392.0	141.5	16.8	501.0	39.2
160.0	12240	192.0	150.1	709.0	549.1	156.0	20.1	553.6	43.2
180.0	12222	> 220	'large'	n/a	n/a	183.7	27.3	655.0	50.9
200.0	12216	> 220	'large'	n/a	n/a	195.0	30.6	696.6	54.2
210.0	12210	> 220	'large'	n/a	n/a	207.8	34.5	742.9	57.9

4.4 Range (working distance) from motor count – dust cover closed

*Analysis of data acquired on Mars show that the relation between a dust-cover-open motor count (m_{open}) and its corresponding dust-cover-closed (m_{closed}) counterpart remains unchanged. As found by Edgett et al. (2019), the relation is: $m_{closed} = 16890 - m_{open}$. This relation can be applied to **Equation 2** to determine working distance for focused images acquired with the WATSON dust cover closed.*

4.4.1 Pre-launch determination

Before launch, instrument characterization testing (Edgett et al., 2019) compared dust cover open and dust cover closed motor count (m_{open} and m_{closed}) positions for targets at the equivalent working distances (d_w) listed in **Table 5** (see also the data in **Table 6**). The observations showed that the relation between motor count (m_{closed}) and working distance (d_w), in centimeters, is best described by the following equation, which relates the dust cover closed to dust cover open stepper motor counts:

$$m_{closed} = 16890 - m_{open}. \quad (3)$$

Equation 3 applies only to the WATSON onboard *Perseverance*, only when the dust cover is closed, and only when the m_{closed} is between ~ 1956 and ~ 4686 . The equation is best used for cases in which d_w is in the 2.5 to ~ 210 cm range. Targets closer or farther from this range cannot be so well determined from motor count. The relation between m_{open} and m_{closed} is portrayed in the plots **Figures 10 and 11** in the black versus blue horizontal axes.

4.4.2 Post-landing assessment

As noted, the WATSON dust cover became coated with a thin film of dust during the rover's final descent to the Martian surface on mission Sol 0 (**Figures 4–6**). Given that the MSL MAHLI dust cover remains coated after > 3170 sols of surface operations, it is anticipated that imaging with the WATSON dust cover closed will be limited. However, it will not be zero, as there are times when MSL MAHLI images are obtained with the dust cover closed so as to protect the lens from fine particulates, especially drill cuttings, during windy conditions.

To assess whether the pre-launch relation between m_{open} and m_{closed} focus positions (**Equation 3**) remains valid on Mars, the data acquired by WATSON on the first sol that the dust cover was opened—Sol 18 (09 March 2021) were evaluated. The camera was positioned ~ 170 cm above the Martian surface, pointed straight down, then the lens was autofocused over the entire field of view with the dust cover closed. The resulting dust-cover-closed image is shown in **Figure 4a**. Then the dust cover was opened, the lens was autofocused over the entire scene, and a second image was acquired (**Figure 4b**). This was followed by a third image (again autofocused over the entire scene) obtained after the dust cover was closed, again. **Table 7** shows that these three images serve to demonstrate that **Equation 3** remains the best understanding of the relation

between m_{closed} and m_{open} for a given focus position corresponding to a given working distance (d_w). In this case:

- The first Sol 18 dust cover closed image found focus, via autofocus, at m_{closed} 4698.
 - The Sol 18 dust cover open image found focus, via autofocus, at m_{open} 12186.
 - Using **Equation 3**, $16890 - 12186 = 4704$, which is within 6 motor counts of 4698. Pre-launch autofocus repeatability experiments (Edgett et al., 2019) showed that a discrepancy of 6 motor counts is typical. The performance is as expected.
- The second Sol 18 dust cover image found focus, via autofocus, at m_{closed} 4704.
 - As noted above, via **Equation 3** and the dust cover m_{open} of 12186, the m_{closed} for this image was expected to be ~ 4704 . Despite the large depth of field at a working distance of 170 cm (**Section 4.5.1**), the autofocused cover-closed image showed zero deviation from the relation between m_{open} and m_{closed} .

Table 5. Data used to establish relation between dust cover closed and dust cover open motor count positions								
date	file name	working distance (cm)	working distance uncertainty (\pm cm)	dust cover closed motor count	dust cover open motor count	motor count \pm uncertainty	calculated cover closed position when difference is 16890	difference, calculated and actual cover-closed motor count
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa019	3.36	0.00	2370		9	2370	0
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa053				14520			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa020	3.87	0.00	2562		9	2556	-6
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa052				14334			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa021	4.38	0.00	2694		15	2730	36
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa051				14160			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa022	4.89	0.00	2856		15	2844	-12
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa050				14046			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa023	5.40	0.00	2958		15	2958	0
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa049				13932			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa024	5.90	0.00	3054		15	3060	6
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa048				13830			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa025	7.17	0.00	3258		15	3282	24
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa046				13608			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa027	8.44	0.00	3432		15	3420	-12
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa045				13470			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa028	9.71	0.00	3546		15	3552	6
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa044				13338			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa029	10.98	0.00	3648		15	3666	18
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa043				13224			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa030	13.52	0.00	3822		15	3810	-12
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa038				13080			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa033	16.06	0.00	3918		18	3924	6
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa037				12966			
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa034	18.60	0.00	4014		18	4014	0
2-Oct-19	wsfocusa036				12876			

Table 6. Pre-launch *Perseverance* WATSON dust cover CLOSED motor count, working distance, and pixel scale observations

date acquired	image ID	motor count	laser range-finding measurement of working distance (cm)	pixel scale measured from image ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa014	0 (close)	1.79	13.1 ± 0.1
03-Oct-2019	wsgrida003	1818	2.35	15.1 ± 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa019	2370	3.36	19.1 ± 0.0
03-Oct-2019	wsgrida004	2364	3.36	19.0 ± 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa020	2562	3.87	21.1 ± 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa021	2694	4.38	22.9 ± 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa022	2856	4.89	24.8 ± 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa023	2958	5.40	26.7 ± 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa024	3054	5.90	28.6 ± 0.1
03-Oct-2019	wsgrida006	3054	5.90	28.4 ± 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa025	3258	7.17	33.2 ± 0.1
03-Oct-2019	wsgrida008	3264	7.17	32.4 ± 0.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa027	3432	8.44	37.7 ± 0.2
03-Oct-2019	wsgrida009	3432	8.44	37.7 ± 0.1
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa028	3546	9.71	42.4 ± 0.2
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa029	3648	10.98	46.7 ± 0.4
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa030	3822	13.52	55.9 ± 0.6
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa033	3918	16.06	65.1 ± 1.0
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa034	4014	18.60	73.7 ± 1.3
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusa035	4020	18.60	73.9 ± 1.3
02-Oct-2019	wsfocusb010	4746	326.41	n/a

Table 7. Sol 18 on-Mars confirmation of the relation (Equation 3) between dust cover closed and dust cover open motor count positions

sol	image ID	working distance (cm)	working distance uncertainty (\pm cm)	dust cover closed motor count	dust cover open motor count	motor count \pm uncertainty	calculated cover closed position when difference is 16890	difference, calculated and actual cover-closed motor count
18	SI0_0018_0668555666_001ECM_N0030578-SRLC08001_0000LUJ03	170	~2	4698		15	4704	6
18	SI0_0018_0668555815_008ECM_N0030578-SRLC08001_0000LUJ03				12186	15		
18	SI0_0018_0668556011_011ECM_N0030578-SRLC08001_0000LUJ01			4704		15	4704	0

4.5 Range (working distance) uncertainty

Range or working distance uncertainty can be estimated using Depth of Field (DOF), as described by Edgett et al. (2015) for MAHLI and Edgett et al. (2019) for WATSON.

However, a different approach is developed, here, that more closely tracks with how the WATSON actually operates when it acquires autofocused images over the $\sim 2.5 - \sim 210$ cm range. This approach estimates working distance uncertainty from motor count uncertainty. Generously, motor count uncertainty is ± 15 .

The sources of uncertainty for the empirical determination of range or working distance (d_w) from WATSON stepper motor count are interrelated. They are as follows:

1. Operational rounding of motor count to the nearest multiple of 6.
 - inherent ± 3 motor counts uncertainty in all cases
2. Repeatability of autofocus motor count determination for a target at fixed range.
 - at least ± 6 motor counts uncertainty in all cases (Edgett et al., 2019).
3. Depth of field (DOF).
 - The farther the subject is from the camera lens, the larger the DOF (**Figures 10 and 11**; Ghaemi, 2009) and the more of the scene is in focus regardless of working distance.
4. Anomalous behavior during stepper motor action (skipped counts or stuck motor)
 - anomalous cases usually do not result in in-focus images unless focused at infinity.

4.5.1 Range uncertainty based on depth of field

Depth of field (DOF) is the distance between the nearest and farthest in-focus feature in a given image. DOF is somewhat subjective, as items that might appear to be in focus to one observer might seem somewhat blurry to another. WATSON DOF increases with working distance (Ghaemi, 2009).

Knowledge of WATSON DOF is important for commanding the acquisition of focus stack images, so as to capture the target surface relief seamlessly while minimizing blurred areas between focus-merged images. DOF can also be used to understand the uncertainty in estimating working distance from motor count (Edgett et al., 2015). Further, as a matter of WATSON tactical operations planning, DOF is considered when the team has to operate within the trade-space between acquisition of focus stack images of a limited number of targets versus imaging a larger number of targets *sans* focus stacks (*i.e.*, for the latter, the camera can image the targets from a greater standoff distance to take advantage of the larger DOF).

As illustrated by Ghaemi (2009) for the MSL MAHLI, with the same optics design as *Perseverance*'s WATSON, the DOF at small working distances (< 12 cm) was defined as the range over which the lens MTF is at > 50% of its peak in-focus value. For targets at a greater range (> 12 cm), Edgett et al. (2019) estimated WATSON DOF using the hyperfocal distance (d_h) equation,

$$d_h = (f_e^2 / f_n c_c) + f_e \quad (4)$$

in which f_e is the lens effective focal length, c_c is the circle of confusion, and f_n is the focal ratio (f/number). For WATSON, f_e and f_n change as a function of focus position. Assuming c_c is a diameter equivalent to two pixel dimensions (*i.e.*, 14.8 μm at the detector surface) provides the best match to the 50% MTF fall-off method at 11.25 cm and is consistent with observations of blurring of near and far objects in MSL MAHLI portraits of the *Curiosity* rover—in those images, two pixels of blur are observed at 1.6 m and two pixels of blur at 14.6 m (Edgett et al., 2015). **Table 8** lists WATSON depth of field estimates obtained by these methods.

Table 8. WATSON depth of field estimates over the 2 to 300 cm range				
working distance (cm)	depth of field (cm)		effective focal length (mm)	focal ratio (f/number)
	near	far		
2.250	-0.041	0.045	18.39	9.80
2.813	-0.052	0.054	18.69	9.52
3.750	-0.071	0.074	19.06	9.22
5.625	-0.124	0.121	19.55	8.91
11.25	-0.390	0.315	20.25	8.63
20	-1.02	1.13	20.59	8.54
40	-3.96	4.94	20.87	8.50
50	-6.06	8.00	20.93	8.49
100	-21.7	38.4	21.09	8.48
150	-44.0	107	21.16	8.47
200	-71.3	248	21.20	8.47
250	-102	561	21.23	8.47
300	-136	1460	21.25	8.47

Pre-launch DOF relation to motor count. Using the pre-launch data for the relation of motor count to working distance (**Table 2**), Edgett et al. (2019) found that the following equation and coefficients describe the relation between motor count (m_{open}) and the range, in centimeters, to the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (5)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 758336$, $b = -235.879$, $c = 2.76772 \times 10^{-2}$, $d = -1.45801 \times 10^{-6}$, and $e = 2.92292 \times 10^{-11}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 755933$, $b = -234.525$, $c = 2.74318 \times 10^{-2}$, $d = -1.43997 \times 10^{-6}$, and $e = 2.87582 \times 10^{-11}$. These values apply only to the WATSON onboard *Perseverance* and only for targets over a working distance range of about 2.5 to 210 cm.

Refinement, post-landing, of DOF relation to motor count. The above coefficients for **Equation 5**, previously presented by Edgett et al. (2019) and Bhartia et al. (2021), are now to be

retired, in favor of revised coefficients determined using the combination of data for the relation between working distance and motor count acquired on Mars as well as Earth (**Tables 2 and 3**).

The revised coefficients, based on the analysis of both the Mars and Earth data, are presented as dashed curves in **Figures 10 and 11**. Again, the equation is the same,

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (6)$$

but the coefficients are now revised to, for d_{near} , $a = 1.1056 \times 10^6$, $b = -337.384$, $c = 3.87806 \times 10^{-2}$, $d = -1.99669 \times 10^{-6}$, and $e = 3.90073 \times 10^{-11}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.1051 \times 10^6$, $b = -336.576$, $c = 3.85941 \times 10^{-2}$, $d = -1.98147 \times 10^{-6}$, and $e = 3.85872 \times 10^{-11}$. And, again, these values apply only to the WATSON onboard *Perseverance* and only for targets over a working distance range of about 2.5 to 210 cm.

4.5.2 Refinement of range uncertainty based on motor count uncertainty

While use of DOF to estimate the working distance uncertainty determined from motor count was recommended by Edgett et al. (2019) and Bhartia et al. (2021)—and has been standard practice for the MSL MAHLI since 2015 (Edgett et al., 2015)—the method to estimate working distance uncertainty is here revised in favor of an approach that actually provides uncertainty estimates that match the observations made during the October 2019 and Sol 78 tests over the operative working distance range (~2.5 to ~210 cm). Use of DOF provides large uncertainty estimates, including negative distances, for larger working distances (e.g., 40–210 cm; **Table 4**), whereas the revised approach, presented here, is directly relatable to the behaviors observed through analysis of sub-framed autofocused WATSON images...

This new approach considers the key sources of motor count uncertainty,

- rounding to the nearest motor count divisible by 6, and
- autofocus repeatability of, typically, ± 6 motor counts,

...to estimate the uncertainty for any given focus motor count determination. The divisible-by-six rule means that any reported motor count may be uncertain by at least ± 3 counts. The autofocus repeatability adds about ± 6 and their uncertainties of ± 3 . To provide a more generous estimate of motor count uncertainty, autofocus repeatability is here considered to be ± 12 , with ± 3 motor counts for the divisible-by-six uncertainty. In other words, all motor count uncertainties are here assumed to be correct to within ± 15 motor count steps.

Application of ± 15 motor counts to the motor count input for **Equation 2** provides estimates of near (–) and far (+) working distance uncertainty. This approach is superior to the use of DOF to estimate working distance uncertainty because it more closely tracks how the camera actually behaves, even at larger working distances in the ~40 to ~210 cm range, when using autofocus sub-frames as observed in the Sol 78 nested imaging of *Nataani* (**Figure 9; Table 3**). At *Nataani*, WATSON found progressively and systematically lower motor counts as working distance increased; the motor counts are not random relative to the large DOF in the 40–210 cm

range. It should also be noted that, at the larger working distances (e.g., 40–210 cm), as working distance increases, the motor count steps per unit of working distance (e.g., centimeter) decreases. Small changes in motor count (at large distances) result in big changes in estimated working distance using **Equation 2**. Assumption of the reasoned motor count uncertainty of ± 15 accommodates the working distance uncertainty.

Figure 12. Rock surface target named *Tsetah* imaged by WATSON on Sol 79 (11 May 2021). The image was focused at motor count m_{open} 13350. Using **Equation 2** and the assumption of a ± 15 motor count uncertainty, the camera was positioned at a working distance of 9.5 ± 0.2 cm. WATSON image S11_0079_0673969227_421ECM_-N0032430SRLC01051_0000LUJ01. The scale bar is based on a pixel scale estimate of $41.5 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$, per **Section 5**.

As an example, consider WATSON image S11_0079_0673969227_421ECM_N0032430-SRLC01051_0000LUJ01, acquired on Sol 79 (**Figure 12**). It shows a rock surface target named *Tsetah* (derived for Mars rover commanding from the Navajo word, *tsétah*, meaning rocky). The camera was focused on this rock by acquiring a 480 x 480 autofocus sub-frame (thumbnail

image S11_0079_0673969217_660ECM_T0032430SRLC01051_000300J01). The autofocus result was a motor count of 13350. With an assumed motor count uncertainty of ± 15 , and **Equation 2**, the camera working distance is estimated to be 9.5 ± 0.2 cm:

- motor count 13350 \rightarrow **Equation 2** \rightarrow 9.52 cm,
- motor count $13350 - 15 = 13335 \rightarrow$ **Equation 2** \rightarrow 9.69 cm,
- motor count $13350 + 15 = 13365 \rightarrow$ **Equation 2** \rightarrow 9.36 cm,
- far uncertainty = $9.69 \text{ cm} - 9.52 \text{ cm} = 0.17 \text{ cm}$, rounded to nearest mm = 0.2 cm,
- near uncertainty = $9.52 \text{ cm} - 9.36 \text{ cm} = 0.16 \text{ cm}$, rounded to nearest mm = 0.2 cm,
 - rounded to nearest mm, result is 9.5 ± 0.2 cm.

Investigators should always keep in mind that the working distance uncertainties determined from motor count are estimates and not always perfect.

5. Refinement – pixel scale from range (working distance)

The analysis described here integrates data acquired on both Mars and Earth to present a revised understanding of the relation between WATSON pixel scale (p_s , in $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) and working distance (d_w , in cm). The relation is a nearly linear curve over the instrument operative range:

$$p_s = a + bd_w + cd_w^2 + dd_w^3 + ed_w^4,$$

in which $a = 6.528$, $b = 3.7261$, $c = -5.7102 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = 4.0576 \times 10^{-5}$, and $e = -8.3282 \times 10^{-8}$.

WATSON CCD pixels are squares of $7.4 \mu\text{m}$ by $7.4 \mu\text{m}$ size. Assuming a flat target surface that is plane-parallel to the CCD, pixel scale (p_s) is the size of the area covered on the target by a single pixel (the square pixel projected as a square onto the target surface). Image scale is the full area of the image (whether 1600 by 1200 pixels or a sub-frame), as projected across the working distance onto a planar target oriented parallel to the CCD.

Actual WATSON targets on Mars are not planes, of course, but knowledge of scale as a function of working distance does permit measurement of the in-focus elements in an image, and these scales are used routinely for science analysis of the data (e.g., for MSL MAHLI, see Weitz et al., 2018). Note that scale is not necessarily equivalent to resolution; the resolution of in-focus elements of a scene is also a function of the camera system's contrast and spatial frequency (i.e., modulation transfer function, MTF; Edgett et al., 2019).

5.1 Pre-launch estimate

The pre-launch WATSON images of targets of known scale (e.g., **Figure 8**) acquired to determine the relation between motor count and working distance (**Table 2**) were also used to empirically determine pixel scale and the relation between pixel scale and working distance (Edgett et al., 2019). The number of pixels across targets of known scale were measured to determine pixel scale (e.g., **Figure 13**). As a result of this effort, Edgett et al. (2019) and Bhartia et al. (2021) reported that the following line equation best fit the observations relating working distance (d_w , in cm) and pixel scale (p_s , in $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$):

$$p_s = 6.7593 + 3.658d_w. \quad (7)$$

Equation 7 applies only to the WATSON onboard *Perseverance*. **Tables 2 and 6** list the images and measurements from those images that were used to determine **Equation 7**. It is important to note that, like the relation between motor count and working distance, the relation to pixel scale (**Equation 7**), is now to be retired in favor of results from the analysis presented in **Section 5.2**.

Figure 13. Example pixel scale measurement of a target of known scale imaged during pre-launch testing at MSSS. This is autofocus sub-frame image wsfocusa046, acquired at MSSS on 02 October 2019 at a motor count m_{open} position of 13609 and a working distance of 7.17 cm. The distance between the yellow arrow tips is 16000 μm and measures 482.51 ± 2 pixels in the image, yielding a pixel scale of 33.2 ± 0.1 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$, as listed in **Table 2**.

5.2 Post-landing refinement

The post-landing assessment and refinement of the relation between WATSON working distance (or range) and pixel scale used both the pre-launch measurements of targets of known scale (**Tables 2 and 6**) and measurements made for targets in the 40 to 210 cm range acquired on Sol 78 at the target named *Nataani* (**Figure 9; Table 3**).

The pixel scale estimates for the 40–210 cm range images of *Nataani* used a principle learned from MSL MAHLI experience (Edgett et al., 2015). That is, knowledge of the scale of the highest spatial resolution WATSON (or MAHLI) images is very good, and the “footprint” of these higher resolution images, when nested within a lower spatial resolution image of the same target, can serve as objects of known scale. This approach worked well for the Sol 78 data, also, because knowledge of working distance and pixel scale of the highest spatial resolution Sol 78 images, acquired at working distance of 3.7 and 6 cm, was excellent, even before the refinements presented here. That is, the pre-launch relation between working distance and pixel scale, **Equation 7**, provides a very good estimate of the scale and dimensions of these higher spatial resolution images.

Figure 14. Measurement of pixel scale for a WATSON image of a rock target named *Nataani* acquired at a working distance of 70 cm using the known dimensions of a higher spatial resolution image acquired at a working distance of 3.7 cm (small inset). The ~ 3.2 by ~ 2.4 cm dimensions of the inset image serve as a “scale bar” to indicate scale of the lower spatial resolution view. Similar measurements for other images acquired at *Nataani* are shown in **Appendix A** and the results are listed in **Table 3**. This is a composite of WATSON images SI1_0078_0673881007-_535ECM_N0032430SRLC00490_0000LUJ01 (3.7 cm working distance) and SI1_0078_0673882176_390ECM-_N0032430-SRLC08002_0000LUJ01 (70 cm working distance).

Figure 14 shows an example in which an image of *Nataani* acquired at a working distance of 3.7 cm was placed within a lower spatial resolution image acquired at a range of 70 cm. The

higher resolution view covers an area of about 3.224 cm by 2.421 cm. Measuring the image dimensions in terms of pixels within the 70 cm working distance image yielded an estimated pixel scale of $253 \pm 5 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$. **Appendix A** shows all of the similar measurements made using Sol 78 images of *Nataani* acquired between 40 and 210 cm working distance.

The refined, post-landing analysis of the relation between pixel scale (p_s , in $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) and working distance (d_w , in cm) is a nearly linear curve as shown in **Figure 15**. The relation is:

$$p_s = a + bd_w + cd_w^2 + dd_w^3 + ed_w^4, \quad (8)$$

in which $a = 6.528$, $b = 3.7261$, $c = -5.7102 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = 4.0576 \times 10^{-5}$, and $e = -8.3282 \times 10^{-8}$.

Equation 8 is only applicable to the WATSON onboard *Perseverance* and is best used for data acquired over the operational range of 2.5 to 210 cm working distance.

Figure 15. Revised relations between working distance and pixel scale for targets up to 250 cm working distance. The solid, nearly-linear curve is **Equation 8**, the relation between pixel scale and working distance. The dashed line envelope represents pixel scale uncertainty, per **Equation 9**. Blue dots are pixel scales measured from images acquired on Earth in October 2019 (**Table 2**) and red dots are pixel scales measured from Sol 78 images of *Nataani* acquired between 40 and 210 cm working distance on Mars (**Table 3**). Where “error bars” are unseen, they are smaller than the plotted data point dot.

5.3 Pixel scale uncertainty

Pixel scale uncertainty can be estimated using Depth of Field (DOF), as described by Edgett et al. (2015) for MAHLI and Edgett et al. (2019) for WATSON.

However, a different approach is developed, here, that more closely tracks with how the WATSON actually operates when it acquires autofocused images over the ~2.5 – ~210 cm range. This approach begins with estimating working distance uncertainty from the ±15 motor count uncertainty. The result for estimated “near” (p_{s_near}) and “far” (p_{s_far}) pixel scale uncertainties is as follows; both curves take the form:

$$p_{s_near} \text{ and } p_{s_far} = a + bd_w + cd_w^2 + dd_w^3 + ed_w^4,$$

in which p_{s_near} and p_{s_far} are in $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$, d_w is in centimeters, and the coefficients for the near (p_{s_near}) uncertainty are $a = 7.1244$, $b = 3.474$, $c = -6.3308 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = 4.4869 \times 10^{-5}$, $e = -9.283 \times 10^{-8}$, and the coefficients for the far (p_{s_far}) uncertainty are $a = 5.897$, $b = 3.9814$, $c = -5.1608 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = 3.6832 \times 10^{-5}$, and $e = -7.5067 \times 10^{-8}$.

5.3.1 Based on depth of field

In the pre-launch analysis (Edgett et al., 2019), the pixel scale uncertainty was estimated using working distance uncertainties (**Section 4.5.2**) computed from motor count. In that report, pixel scale uncertainty was determined by applying **Equation 7** to the \pm working distance determined from near (–) and far (+) depth of field (DOF). This is the approach that has been in use for the MSL MAHLI since 2015 (Edgett et al., 2015) and works reasonably well for WATSON at small working distances (e.g., ~2.5 to ~15 cm; Edgett et al., 2019). **Table 4** shows examples, in the “pre-launch equations” column, of the application of this approach to pixel scale uncertainty estimation. While it works well for small working distances, it results in unrealistically large uncertainties for images at greater ranges, such as 40–210 cm.

5.3.2 Refinement based on motor count uncertainty

Owing to the large uncertainties in estimated pixel scale in the 40–210 cm working distance range, a new approach was developed that traces back to the earlier discussion that each reported motor count has an uncertainty of about ± 15 counts (**Section 4.5.2**). The ± 15 motor counts were applied to each case for which a measurement of pixel scale was determined from an image acquired on Mars or Earth (**Tables 2, 3, and 6**). These were then used to determine the shape of near-linear curves in the same form as **Equation 8**. The result for “near” (p_{s_near}) and “far” (p_{s_far}) pixel scale uncertainties is as follows; both curves take the form:

$$p_{s_near} \text{ and } p_{s_far} = a + bd_w + cd_w^2 + dd_w^3 + ed_w^4, \quad (9)$$

in which p_{s_near} and p_{s_far} are in $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$, d_w is in centimeters, and the coefficients for the near (p_{s_near}) uncertainty are $a = 7.1244$, $b = 3.474$, $c = -6.3308 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = 4.4869 \times 10^{-5}$,

$e = -9.283 \times 10^{-8}$, and the coefficients for the far (p_{s_far}) uncertainty are $a = 5.897$, $b = 3.9814$, $c = -5.1608 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = 3.6832 \times 10^{-5}$, and $e = -7.5067 \times 10^{-8}$. These uncertainties are shown as dashed curves in **Figure 15**.

For pixel scales related to working distances found by **Equation 2** that are < 2.7 cm, the uncertainty is automatically estimated to be $\pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$; this is based on MSL MAHLI as well as WATSON pre-launch experience. In addition, WATSON will rarely, if ever, be operated at working distances < 2.7 cm on Mars. **Equation 9** is only applicable to the WATSON onboard *Perseverance* and is best used for data acquired over the operational range of 2.5 to 210 cm working distance. Investigators should always keep in mind that the pixel scale uncertainties are estimates and not always perfect.

5.4 Post-landing range and scale check

And end-to-end check to estimate working distance and pixel scale from motor count, and compare the results with pixel scale determined by measuring features of known scale in WATSON images, was performed using WATSON images of the SHERLOC and PIXL calibration targets acquired on Sols 26, 62, and 97.

The measured pixel scales are generally within the range of uncertainty for pixel scales computed from motor count and working distance; a couple of exceptions were only 0.1 to 0.2 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ outside the measured range.

These observations provide confirmation that the revised approaches for determining working distance and pixel scale for WATSON images, presented in this report, work well and provide realistic results with adequate estimates of uncertainty.

Performance of the newly refined equations relating motor count to working distance (**Equations 2, 3, and 6**) and working distance to pixel scale (**Equations 8 and 9**) can be assessed by determining pixel scale for images acquired on Mars of objects of known scale and comparing with results derived from the image focus motor count. In particular, WATSON imaged the SHERLOC and PIXL calibration targets (Bhartia et al., 2021; Allwood et al., 2020) on Sols 26, 62, and 97 (**Figure 16**). **Table 9** summarizes the observations; objects of known scale were measured as a function of pixels across them using the Sols 26, 62, and 97 images (**Appendix B**), then these results were compared with pixel scales determined from each image's reported focus motor count. As shown in the rightmost column of **Table 9**, and the plot in **Figure 17**, the measurements from these calibration targets fall within (or very close to, within $0.2 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$, of) the expected uncertainty range for pixel scale and working distance at each target.

Figure 16. Top – SHERLOC calibration target onboard the Perseverance rover, as imaged on Mars using WATSON on Sol 26 (mosaic of images SI1_0026_0669253636_115ECM_N0030792SRLC07004_0000LUJ02, SI1_0026_0669253775_136ECM_N0030792SRLC07004_0000LUJ02, and SI1_0026_0669253923_158ECM_N0030792SRLC07004_0000LUJ02). **Bottom** –PIXL calibration target as photographed on Earth before launch.

Table 9. Pixel scale measured from images vs. determined from working distance derived from motor count for WATSON images of the SHERLOC and PIXL calibration targets on Mars

target	sol	WATSON image ID	motor count		intended working distance*	pixel scale measured from WATSON image		working distance determined from motor count		pixel scale from working distance determined from motor count		relation of measured pixel scale to computed pixel scale
			value	± uncertainty	cm	µm/-pixel	± µm/-pixel	cm	± cm	µm/-pixel	± µm/-pixel	
SHERLOC meteorite	26	SI1_0026_0669254065_127EC M_N0030792SRLC07006_000 0LUJ01	13986	15	5.0	24.6	0.0	5.1	0.1	25.5	0.7	outside estimated uncertainty by 0.2 µm/pixel
SHERLOC meteorite	62	SI1_0062_0672457451_855EC M_N0032046SRLC07024_000 0LUJ01	13968	15	5.0	24.9	0.0	5.2	0.1	25.8	0.7	outside estimated uncertainty by 0.1 µm/pixel
SHERLOC maze	26	SI1_0026_0669254211_189EC M_N0030792SRLC07005_000 0LUJ01	13992	15	5.0	24.8	0.0	5.1	0.1	25.4	0.7	within the computed uncertainty range
SHERLOC maze	62	SI1_0062_0672457589_789EC M_N0032046SRLC07025_000 0LUJ01	13980	15	5.0	24.8	0.0	5.2	0.1	25.6	0.7	within the computed uncertainty range
SHERLOC geocache coin	62	SI1_0062_0672457751_375EC M_N0032046SRLC07026_000 0LUJ01	13986	15	5.0	24.9	0.0	5.1	0.1	25.5	0.7	within the computed uncertainty range
PIXL target	26	SI1_0026_0669254766_116EC M_N0030792SRLC07007_000 0LUJ01	13602	15	7.0	32.6	0.5	7.3	0.1	33.4	1.3	within the computed uncertainty range
PIXL target	97	SI1_0097_0675549107_023EC M_N0040136SRLC07031_000 0LUJ01	13608	15	7.0	32.9	0.4	7.2	0.1	33.2	1.3	within the computed uncertainty range
SHERLOC mosaic 1 of 3	26	SI1_0026_0669253636_115EC M_N0030792SRLC07004_000 0LUJ01	13152	15	12.0	49.8	0.1	12.1	0.2	51.0	2.5	within the computed uncertainty range
SHERLOC mosaic 1 of 3	62	SI1_0062_0672457056_570EC M_N0032046SRLC07023_000 0LUJ01	13140	15	12.0	50.1	0.1	12.3	0.2	51.7	2.6	within the computed uncertainty range
SHERLOC mosaic 2 of 3	26	SI1_0026_0669253775_136EC M_N0030792SRLC07004_000 0LUJ01	13158	15	12.0	49.9	0.1	12.0	0.2	50.7	2.5	within the computed uncertainty range
SHERLOC mosaic 2 of 3	62	SI1_0062_0672457182_414EC M_N0032046SRLC07023_000 0LUJ01	13146	15	12	50.3	0.1	12.2	0.2	51.4	2.6	within the computed uncertainty range
SHERLOC mosaic 3 of 3	26	SI1_0026_0669253923_158EC M_N0030792SRLC07004_000 0LUJ01	13158	15	12	49.6	0.1	12.0	0.2	50.7	2.5	within the computed uncertainty range
SHERLOC mosaic 3 of 3	62	SI1_0062_0672457316_359EC M_N0032046SRLC07023_000 0LUJ01	13146	15	12	50.0	0.1	12.2	0.2	51.4	2.6	within the computed uncertainty range
SHERLOC full target	26	SI1_0026_0669253495_138EC M_N0030792SRLC07003_000 0LUJ01	12606	15	31.5	117.0	1.0	32.3	1.2	122.2	8.1	within the computed uncertainty range
SHERLOC full target (stereo-1)	62	SI1_0062_0672456826_566EC M_N0032046SRLC07022_000 0LUJ01	12600	15	31.5	117.0	1.0	32.8	1.3	124.0	8.2	within the computed uncertainty range

* intended working distance is the intent when the robotic arm positioned WATSON to acquire the image; actual working distance is likely to differ from this by some number of millimeters.

Figure 17. Pixel scales measured from Sol 26, 62, and 97 WATSON images of SHERLOC and PIXL calibration target elements (red dots and error bars) as listed in **Table 9** and shown in **Appendix B**, as a function of working distance computed from motor count. The results fall within the refined/ revised expected range (solid line plus dashed lines for uncertainty range) for the relations between pixel scale and working distance presented in this report (**Equations 8 and 9**). Where “error bars” are unseen, they are smaller than the plotted data point dot.

6. Particulates on the WATSON detector

Small particulates accumulated on the WATSON CCD during thermal testing before and after delivery to SHERLOC engineers at JPL during the October through December 2019 period. The single largest particle is about 74 by 30 μm in size; the majority are smaller than or near the size of the detector's 7.4 μm pixels.

WATSON sky flat field imaging performed on Sol 77 on Mars shows that no new particulates accumulated on the CCD during ATLO testing, launch, interplanetary cruise, and spacecraft entry, descent, and landing on Mars. None of the particles already present at the end of December 2019 moved during this period.

More than 3170 sols of MSL MAHLI operations suggests the particles on the WATSON CCD will continue to remain in-place, not move, and that no new particles will accumulate during the surface mission.

6.1 Introduction and purpose

The WATSON image sensor is an ON Semiconductor (formerly Truesense Imaging; formerly Kodak) KAI-2020CM charge-coupled device (CCD) without a cover glass. The sensor has 1640 by 1214 pixels of 7.4 μm by 7.4 μm size. The photoactive area is a 1600 by 1200 pixels area inside of 16 dark columns and 4 photoactive buffer pixel columns on either side of the detector, 2 dark rows at the top and 4 dark rows at the bottom, plus 4 photoactive buffer pixel rows at both the top and bottom of the detector. Color imaging is achieved on the detector using red, green, blue (RGB) filtered microlenses arranged in a Bayer pattern.

Without a cover glass, the potential for small particles to accumulate on the CCD is a known problem that occurred with the MSL MAHLI, its testbed counterpart, as well as both the WATSON onboard *Perseverance* and its testbed counterpart. The challenge is to prevent or minimize particulate accumulation during manufacture, and every precaution was taken. Nevertheless, WATSON images exhibit dark spots that result from the presence of tiny particles on the CCD (Figures 18–20).

6.2 Pre-launch condition

6.2.1 Before shipment from MSSS

WATSON was assembled in August 2019 and tested at Malin Space Science Systems (MSSS) during September and October 2019. These activities included vibration testing (simulating launch), thermal-vacuum testing, and instrument calibration and characterization (Edgett et al., 2019). When the camera was first assembled, the CCD was clean. Vibration testing introduced a

few very small particles (Edgett et al., 2019), but thermal-vacuum testing introduced many small particles. Most of them are ≤ 1 pixel in size ($\leq 7.4 \mu\text{m}$ in size); the largest cover areas of < 5 by 3 pixels. Some particles are opaque, others are transparent, either because of their size, shape, or inherent transparency. The yellow circles in Figure 18 indicate the locations of particulates on the CCD at just before the instrument was delivered to the SHERLOC engineers at the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL).

Figure 18. Yellow circles indicate locations of small particulates on the WATSON CCD as of the time the instrument was delivered from MSSS to JPL. Most of the particles are small, ≤ 1 pixel ($\leq 7.4 \mu\text{m}$) in size. The largest is about 5 by 3 pixels in size. Some are opaque, some are transparent. This is WATSON calibration image wsflatb031, acquired on 09 October 2019 at MSSS. The image was converted to grayscale after Bayer pattern color interpolation to provide a view that can be readily compared with **Figures 19 and 20**.

6.2.2 Before delivery to ATLO

After the WATSON camera head was delivered to SHERLOC engineers at JPL for installation on the SHERLOC Turret Assembly (**Figure 1**), the instrument underwent testing which included time spent in a thermal vacuum chamber. As occurred during thermal-vacuum testing at MSSS

(Section 6.2.1; Edgett et al., 2019), additional particles that had been trapped inside the camera during manufacture migrated to the surface of the CCD.

As indicated by red arrows in **Figure 19**, two of the particles are noticeably large and the largest is near the center of the CCD. The larger one is about 10 by 4 pixels (~ 74 by ~ 30 μm) in size, the smaller of the two covers about 5 by 5 pixels (~ 37 by ~ 37 μm). Other, smaller particles also accumulated (**Figure 19**).

Figure 19. Blue circles indicate particles that accumulated on the WATSON CCD during the November–December 2019 period after delivery to the SHERLOC team at JPL. Most of the particles deposited on the CCD during that time were small (≤ 7.4 μm in size), but two of them (red arrows) are noticeably larger. The yellow circles are the same as in Figure 18; they indicate the particulates that accumulated on the CCD before delivery to JPL, during the September–October 2019 period. This is WATSON ATLO test image CDPID-1403, acquired on 04 January 2020 after the SHERLOC Turret Assembly (Figure 1) was installed on the Perseverance rover at JPL. The image was converted to grayscale after Bayer pattern color interpolation to provide a view that can be readily compared with **Figures 18 and 20**.

6.2.3 In ATLO

Monitoring of WATSON images acquired during Assembly, Testing, and Launch Operations (ATLO) showed no new particulate accumulation, nor did any of the particles move.

6.3 Post-launch and landing state

Figure 20 shows a WATSON sky flat field image acquired on Mars on mission Sol 77 (08 May 2021). As of this time, no new particles were observed. No new particles accumulated on the CCD despite the vigor of launch, the nature of the interplanetary cruise environment, and the events of the rover’s entry, descent, and landing on Mars in February 2021. Not only did no new particles accumulate, but also none of the preceding particles—all of them deposited before the instrument was delivered to ATLO in January 2020—move.

Figure 20. WATSON sky flat field image acquired on Mars on Sol 77 (08 May 2021). No new particles accumulated or moved since before January 2020. There was no impact as a result of launch, cruise, or entry, descent, and landing on Mars. Blue circles indicate particles that accumulated during November–December 2019; yellow indicate the particles that accumulated September–October 2019. This is WATSON image S11_0077_0673784682_632ECM-_N0032430SRLC07028_0000LUJ01. The image was converted to grayscale after Bayer pattern color interpolation to provide a view that can be readily compared with **Figures 18 and 19**.

MSL MAHLI experience, covering > 3170 sols of operation on Mars, suggests the particles on the WATSON CCD are not likely to move and none are likely to accumulate during surface operations. The MAHLI experience was the same as that of the WATSON — no new particles accumulated and no particles moved as a result of launch, cruise, and Mars landing events.

Sky flat field images will be acquired periodically during *Perseverance*'s continuing mission on Mars; these will also be used to monitor for changes in the particulates on the CCD.

6.4 Impact of particulates on CCD

As with MSL MAHLI experience (Edgett et al., 2015), the presence of the particulates on the WATSON CCD does not impact the science and engineering value of the images. Indeed, they are blemishes that can be removed by simple image processing (using the DN values of nearest-neighbor pixels). **Figure 21** shows an example based on the WATSON image of a rock on Mars shown previously in **Figure 12**.

Figure 21. Rock target named *Tsetah* imaged by WATSON on Sol 79 (11 May 2021), same as shown in **Figure 12**, except that the two largest blemishes (particles on the CCD) have been cosmetically removed. The two insets show the largest blemish before and after removal. These blemishes do not impact the science and engineering value of WATSON images. WATSON image S11_0079_0673969227_421ECM_-N0032430SRLC01051_0000LUJ01.

7. Summary

The equations and coefficients that relate WATSON focus motor count to working distance (range) and pixel scale have been refined relative to the pre-launch assessment of Edgett et al. (2019) using a combination of pre-launch data and images acquired on Mars. A check of the performance of these revised equations and coefficients, using WATSON images of the SHERLOC and PIXL calibration targets, provide expected results within the range of known uncertainties (“error bars”).

The particles that accumulated on the WATSON CCD during the September–December 2019 period have remained unchanged following ATLO testing, launch, interplanetary cruise, entry, descent, and landing on Mars. No new particles were deposited and no particles have moved since the instrument was installed on the rover in January 2020. MSL MAHLI experience over > 3170 sols on Mars suggests that the particles on the WATSON CCD will remain in-place, and no new particles will accumulate, for the duration of *Perseverance*’s activities on Mars.

Acknowledgements

Most of the analysis and refinement reported here was completed in June and July 2021. K.D. Supulver provided invaluable assistance with plot creation and determination of the equations to relate WATSON stepper motor count to working distance and depth of field. M.A. Caplinger acquired the pre-launch WATSON October 2019 focus-range-pixel-scale test data. SHERLOC engineers at JPL acquired the ATLO test image to document particles that accumulated on the CCD. WATSON operations on Mars has involved the SHERLOC Imaging Operations Lead, M.R. Kennedy (Wu), along with uplink and downlink engineers including J. Huggett, B. Nixon, A. Werynski, K. Winchell, W. Yingling, D. Krysak, A. Magee.

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Appendix A – Pixel scale analysis of Sol 78 Nataani images

The following figures show the measurements made to estimate pixel scale from images acquired at 40 to 210 cm working distance of the rock target, *Nataani*, on Sol 78 by WATSON on the surface of Mars.

40 cm standoff

70 cm standoff

100 cm standoff

150 cm standoff

170 cm standoff

200 cm standoff

210 cm standoff – pixel scale determined using 3.7 cm standoff image

210 cm standoff – pixel scale determined using 10 cm standoff image

Appendix B – Measured pixel scales of WATSON images of the SHERLOC and PIXL calibration targets

The following figures show the measurements made to estimate pixel scale from images of the SHERLOC and PIXL calibration targets acquired on Sols 26, 62, and 97 by WATSON on the surface of Mars.

Sol 26 – SHERLOC meteorite target

~5 cm standoff

Sol 26 – SHERLOC intensity maze target

~5 cm standoff

Sol 26 – SHERLOC calibration target, mosaic image 1 of 3

~12 cm standoff

Sol 26 – SHERLOC calibration target, mosaic image 2 of 3

~12 cm standoff

Sol 26 – SHERLOC calibration target, mosaic image 3 of 3

~12 cm standoff

Sol 26 – SHERLOC calibration target

~31.5 cm standoff

Sol 26 – PIXL calibration target

~7 cm standoff

Sol 62 – SHERLOC meteorite target

~5 cm standoff

Sol 62 – SHERLOC intensity maze target

~5 cm standoff

Sol 62 – SHERLOC geocache coin target

~5 cm standoff

Sol 62 – SHERLOC calibration target, mosaic image 1 of 3

~12 cm standoff

Sol 62 – SHERLOC calibration target, mosaic image 2 of 3

~12 cm standoff

Sol 62 – SHERLOC calibration target, mosaic image 3 of 3

~12 cm standoff

Sol 62 – SHERLOC calibration target (stereo-1 view)

~31.5 cm standoff

Sol 97 – PIXL calibration target

~7 cm standoff

-end-